

Gene Lists for Analysis

1. Negative Controls: Housekeeping Genes

Ribosomal Large Subunit: RPL3, RPL4, RPL5, RPL6, RPL7, RPL7A, RPL8, RPL9, RPL10, RPL10A, RPL11, RPL12, RPL13, RPL13A, RPL14, RPL15, RPL17, RPL18, RPL18A, RPL19, RPL21, RPL22, RPL23, RPL23A

Ribosomal Small Subunit: RPS2, RPS3, RPS3A, RPS4X, RPS4Y1, RPS5, RPS6, RPS7, RPS8, RPS9, RPS10, RPS11, RPS12, RPS13, RPS14, RPS15, RPS15A, RPS16, RPS17, RPS18, RPS19, RPS20, RPS21

Cytoskeletal Actin: ACTB, ACTG1, ACTA1, ACTA2, ACTC1, ACTN1, ACTN2, ACTN4, PFN1, PFN2

Cytoskeletal Tubulin: TUBA1A, TUBA1B, TUBA1C, TUBA3C, TUBA3D, TUBA4A, TUBA8, TUBB, TUBB1, TUBB2A, TUBB2B, TUBB3, TUBB4A, TUBB4B, TUBB6

Glycolysis: HK1, HK2, GPI, PFKM, PFKP, PFKL, ALDOA, ALDOB, ALDOC, TPI1, GAPDH, PGK1, PGK2, PGAM1, PGAM2, ENO1, ENO2, ENO3, PKM, PKLR, LDHA, LDHB, LDHC

TCA Cycle: CS, ACO1, ACO2, IDH1, IDH2, IDH3A, IDH3B, IDH3G, OGDH, SUCLA2, SUCLG1, SUCLG2, SDHA, SDHB, SDHC, SDHD, FH, MDH1, MDH2

Mitochondrial Complex I: NDUFA1, NDUFA2, NDUFA3, NDUFA4, NDUFA5, NDUFA6, NDUFA7, NDUFA8, NDUFA9, NDUFA10, NDUFA11, NDUFA12, NDUFA13, NDUFB1, NDUFB2, NDUFB3, NDUFB4, NDUFB5, NDUFB6

Mitochondrial Complex IV: COX4I1, COX4I2, COX5A, COX5B, COX6A1, COX6A2, COX6B1, COX6B2, COX6C, COX7A1, COX7A2, COX7A2L, COX7B, COX7C, COX8A, COX8C

ATP Synthase: ATP5F1A, ATP5F1B, ATP5F1C, ATP5F1D, ATP5F1E, ATP5MC1, ATP5MC2, ATP5MC3, ATP5MD, ATP5ME, ATP5MF, ATP5MG, ATP5PB, ATP5PD, ATP5PF, ATP5PO

Heat Shock Proteins: HSPA1A, HSPA1B, HSPA1L, HSPA2, HSPA4, HSPA4L, HSPA5, HSPA6, HSPA8, HSPA9, HSPA12A, HSPA12B, HSPA13, HSP90AA1, HSP90AB1, HSP90B1, HSPH1

2. Monoamines

Dopamine Receptors: DRD1, DRD2, DRD3, DRD4, DRD5

Dopamine Synthesis & Metabolism: TH, DDC, COMT, MAOA, MAOB, DBH, GCH1, PTS, QDPR, SPR

Dopamine Transport & Signaling: SLC6A3, SLC18A1, SLC18A2, PPP1R1B, GNAL, ADCY5, PDE1B, PDE10A

Serotonin Receptors: HTR1A, HTR1B, HTR1D, HTR1E, HTR1F, HTR2A, HTR2B, HTR2C, HTR3A, HTR3B, HTR3C, HTR3D, HTR3E, HTR4, HTR5A, HTR5BP, HTR6, HTR7

Serotonin Synthesis & Metabolism: TPH1, TPH2, SLC6A4, AANAT, ASMT

Norepinephrine Receptors: ADRA1A, ADRA1B, ADRA1D, ADRA2A, ADRA2B, ADRA2C, ADRB1, ADRB2, ADRB3

Norepinephrine Synthesis & Transport: PNMT, SLC6A2

Histamine System: HRH1, HRH2, HRH3, HRH4, HDC, HNMT, SLC22A3

Trace Amine Receptors: TAAR1, TAAR2, TAAR5, TAAR6, TAAR8, TAAR9

Monoamine Signaling: GNB1, GNB2, GNB3, GNB4, GNB5, GNG2, GNG3, GNG4, GNG7, GNG11, GNG12, ADCY1, ADCY2, ADCY7, ADCY8, ADCY9, PDE4A, PDE4B, PDE4C, PDE4D

Vesicular Transport: SYT1, SYT2, SYT4, SYT7, SYT11, SNAP25, VAMP2, STX1A, STX1B, CPLX1, CPLX2

3. Neurosteroids

Cholesterol Transport & Mitochondrial Import: STAR (steroidogenic acute regulatory protein), TSPO (translocator protein 18kDa), TSPO2, VDAC1, VDAC2, VDAC3, ANT1 (SLC25A4), ANT2 (SLC25A5), ACBD1 (DBI/ACBP, endozepine precursor), ACBD3, NPC1, NPC2, STARD1, STARD3, STARD4, STARD5, STARD6

Mitochondrial Electron Transfer: FDX1, FDX2, FDXR, POR, CYB5A, CYB5R3

Cholesterol Biosynthesis (Terminal Steps): HMGCR, HMGCS1, MVK, PMVK, MVD, IDI1, IDI2, FDPS, FDFT1, SQLE, LSS, CYP51A1, TM7SF2, MSMO1, NSDHL, HSD17B7, SC5D, DHCR7, DHCR24, EBP

Side-Chain Cleavage: CYP11A1 (P450_{scc})

3 β -HSD/Isomerase: HSD3B1, HSD3B2, HSD3B7

17 α -Hydroxylase/Lyase: CYP17A1

17 β -Hydroxysteroid Dehydrogenases: HSD17B1, HSD17B2, HSD17B3, HSD17B4, HSD17B6, HSD17B7, HSD17B8, HSD17B10 (ABAD/SCHAD), HSD17B11, HSD17B12, HSD17B13, HSD17B14

5 α -Reductases: SRD5A1, SRD5A2, SRD5A3

5 β -Reductase: AKR1D1

3 α -HSD (AKR1C Family): AKR1C1, AKR1C2, AKR1C3, AKR1C4

20 α -HSD: AKR1C1, CBR1

11 β -Hydroxysteroid Dehydrogenases: HSD11B1, HSD11B2, HSD11B1L

Aromatase: CYP19A1

Adrenal Steroidogenic CYPs: CYP11B1, CYP11B2, CYP21A2

Steroid Sulfotransferases: SULT1E1, SULT2A1, SULT2B1, SULT1A1

Steroid Sulfatase: STS

Steroid UGTs: UGT1A1, UGT1A4, UGT2B7, UGT2B15, UGT2B17, UGT2B4

Steroid-Metabolizing CYPs (Non-Classic): CYP7A1, CYP7B1, CYP27A1, CYP46A1, CYP39A1, CYP3A4, CYP3A5, CYP3A7, CYP2D6, CYP1A1, CYP1A2, CYP1B1

Nuclear Steroid Receptors: ESR1, ESR2, AR, PGR, NR3C1, NR3C2

Steroid Receptor Coregulators: NCOA1, NCOA2, NCOA3, NCOR1, NCOR2, NRIP1, PNRC1, PNRC2, PELP1

Membrane Progesterone Receptors: PGRMC1, PGRMC2, PAQR5, PAQR6, PAQR7, PAQR8, PAQR9

Membrane Estrogen Receptor: GPER1 (GPR30)

Membrane Androgen-Related: GPRC6A, OXER1, ZIP9 (SLC39A9)

Steroid Binding Proteins: SHBG, SERPINA6 (CBG), ALB, AFP, TTR

Steroid Chaperones: FKBP4, FKBP5, PPID, PTGES3

GABA-A Receptor Subunits (Neurosteroid-Sensitive): GABRA2, GABRA3, GABRA4, GABRA5, GABRA6, GABRB1, GABRB3, GABRD, GABRE, GABRG1, GABRG2, GABRG3, GABRP, GABRQ, GABRR1, GABRR2, GABRR3

Sigma Receptors: SIGMAR1, TMEM97

Xenobiotic/Steroid Receptors: NR1I2 (PXR), NR1I3 (CAR)

Oxysterol Receptors: NR1H3 (LXR α), NR1H2 (LXR β)

Neurosteroid Transporters: ABCB1, ABCC1, ABCC4, ABCG2, SLC22A8, SLC22A6, SLCO1A2, SLCO2B1, SLC10A1, SLC10A6

Neurosteroid Transcription Factors: SF1 (NR5A1), LRH1 (NR5A2), DAX1 (NR0B1), GATA4, GATA6, SP1, SREBF1, SREBF2, NR4A1, NR4A2

Endozepines: DBI (ACBP)

Neurosteroid Signaling Kinases: SRC, MAPK1, MAPK3, PIK3R1

Additional Steroid Reductases: DHRS9, DHRS4, RDH5, WWOX, PECR

4. Glutamatergics

NMDA Receptors: GRIN1, GRIN2A, GRIN2B, GRIN2C, GRIN2D, GRIN3A, GRIN3B

AMPA Receptors: GRIA1, GRIA2, GRIA3, GRIA4

Kainate Receptors: GRIK1, GRIK2, GRIK3, GRIK4, GRIK5

Delta Receptors: GRID1, GRID2

Glutamate Receptor Interacting: GRIP1, GRIP2, PICK1, SHANK1, SHANK2, SHANK3, HOMER1, HOMER2, HOMER3, DLGAP1, DLGAP2, DLGAP3, DLGAP4, DLG1, DLG2, DLG3, DLG4

Glutamate Transporters: SLC1A1, SLC1A2, SLC1A3, SLC1A6, SLC1A7, SLC17A6, SLC17A7, SLC17A8

Glutamate Metabolism: GLUL, GLS, GLS2, GLUD1, GLUD2, GAD1, GAD2

BDNF-TrkB Pathway: BDNF, NTRK2, NGF, NTRK1, NTF3, NTRK3, NTF4

mTOR Pathway: MTOR, RPTOR, RICTOR, MLST8, AKT1, AKT2, AKT3, PIK3CA, PIK3CB, PIK3CD, PIK3CG, PTEN, TSC1, TSC2, RHEB, RPS6KB1, RPS6KB2, EIF4EBP1, EIF4E

CREB Pathway: CREB1, CREB3, CREB5, ATF1, ATF2, ATF3, ATF4, CREBBP, EP300, CRTIC1, CRTIC2, CRTIC3

Immediate Early Genes: ARC, FOS, FOSB, FOSL1, FOSL2, JUN, JUNB, JUND, EGR1, EGR2, EGR3, EGR4, NPAS4

CaMKII Signaling: CAMK2A, CAMK2B, CAMK2D, CAMK2G, CAMK4, CALM1, CALM2, CALM3, CALML3, CALML4, CALML5, CALML6

PKA-PKC Signaling: PRKACA, PRKACB, PRKACG, PRKAR1A, PRKAR1B, PRKAR2A, PRKAR2B, PRKCA, PRKCB, PRKCG, PRKCD, PRKCE

Sigma-Metabolic: SIGMAR1, CYP2D6, CYP3A4, CYP2B6, CYP2C19

5. Pruning

Complement System: C1QA, C1QB, C1QC, C3, C4A, C4B, ITGAM, ITGB2, C3AR1, MASP1, MASP2, CFH, CFI, CFB, SERPING1

Microglial Signaling & Phagocytosis: CX3CR1, CX3CL1, TREM2, TYROBP, CD68, MERTK, AXL, TYRO3, GAS6, PROS1, MEGF10, GULP1, ABCA1, CD36, CD47, P2RY12, P2RY6, TMEM119

Classical Synaptic Pruning (Adhesion): NRXN1, NRXN2, NRXN3, NLGN1, NLGN2, NLGN3, NLGN4X, CBLN1, CBLN2, CBLN4

Semaphorin-Plexin Signaling: SEMA3A, SEMA3F, SEMA4D, SEMA6A, SEMA7A, PLXNA1, PLXNA2, PLXNA3, PLXNA4, PLXNB1, PLXNB2, NRP1, NRP2

Ephrin Signaling: EPHA4, EPHA7, EPHB1, EPHB2, EPHB3, EFNA1, EFNA2, EFNA3, EFNA4, EFNA5, EFNB1, EFNB2, EFNB3

WNT Signaling: WNT5A, WNT7A, WNT7B, FZD3, FZD5, RYK, LRP6, DVL1, GSK3B, CTNNB1, APC

TGF- β /BMP Signaling: TGFB1, TGFB2, TGFBR1, TGFBR2, BMP4, BMP7, BMPR1A, BMPR2, SMAD2, SMAD3, SMAD4

Apoptotic & Caspase Pathways: CASP3, CASP6, CASP9, BAX, BAK1, BCL2, BCL2L1, APAF1, XIAP, DFNA5

Ubiquitin-Proteasome System: UBE3A, FBXO45, MIB1, SMURF1, SMURF2, NEDD4, TRIM3, MYCBP2, USP14

Cytoskeletal Remodeling: RHOA, RAC1, CDC42, ROCK1, ROCK2, LIMK1, CFL1, CFL2, PAK1, ARPC2, WASF1, DAAM1

MHC Class I Molecules: B2M, HLA-A, HLA-B, HLA-C, TAP1, TAP2, PSMB8, PSMB9, CD3Z, LILRB3

Autophagy-Related: ATG5, ATG7, ATG12, BECN1, ULK1, MAP1LC3A, MAP1LC3B, SQSTM1, AMBRA1, RUBCN

Matrix Metalloproteinases: MMP2, MMP9, MMP14, TIMP1, TIMP2, ADAM10, ADAM17, ADAMTS4

Cell Adhesion Molecules: NCAM1, L1CAM, CNTN1, CNTN2, CDH2, PCDH10, PCDHGA1, PCDHGB1, PCDHGC3

Lipid Signaling: APOE, CLU, LDLR, LRP1, ABCA7, PLCG1, DGKZ

Ion Channels & Receptors (Non-Glutamatergic): GABRA1, GABRB2, GABBR1, KCNJ10, SCN1A, CACNA1C, HCN1

Immune/Inflammatory Modulators: IL1B, IL6, IL10, TNF, IFNG, STAT3, RELA, NFKB1, TLR2, TLR4, NLRP3

Activity-Dependent & Developmental Regulators: SYNGAP1, FMR1, MECP2, LYNX1, OTX2, PVALB, SLC32A1, NPTX2, PENK

Astrocyte-Related: SPARC, SPARCL1, THBS1, THBS2, THBS4, GFAP, AQP4, GJA1

Schizophrenia/Disorder-Associated: CSMD1, MIR137, ZNF804A, DISC1, ERBB4, NRG1, RELN, TCF4

Additional Pruning Regulators: CYFIP1, DSCAM, SDK1, SDK2
